

A cultural and glocalized approach to the maker movement: An ethnomathematical perspective

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The maker movement has faced constant criticism for not considering the existing making practices in the context of people of diverse cultural and ethnic groups. Nonetheless, it is quintessential that the teaching and learning of STEM be done in terms of situating it in diverse socio-cultural contexts. This situation has informed the current study to attempt a cultural and glocalized form of approaching 'making' through the lens of ethnomathematics. By combining methods from Gerdes, Bishop and Vygotsky in the sphere of ethnographic, design-based and activity inquiries, this conceptual paper conceptualizes what doing STEM through the existing making practices in the context of people of diverse cultural and ethnic groups is and how that can also supplement, inform and centre stage the global practices of conventional making. Thus, a conceptual framework for cultural and glocalized approach to the maker movement in the lens of ethnomathematics and its sister disciplines is developed.

Introduction

Makerspaces are learner-centric physical areas where individuals develop ideas, experiment, tinker, design, and create artifacts using digital and physical tools to represent their learning (see Pocock, 2016) in computational thinking, STEM, etc. To this, makerspaces have helped to refute the notion that STEM is about following some set of rules and principles which are abstract. Though, Dougherty (2012) asserts that the term maker is universal and core to human identity and Wing (2011) defined computational thinking (CT) to suggest that to teach or learn CT computers are not necessarily needed and also CT entails one's ability to design solutions that can be executed by a computer, a human, or a combination of both. And again, the National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM, 1991) and other researchers have highlighted, in their guidelines, the importance of building connections between mathematics and students' personal lives and cultures (see D'Ambrosio, 1990; Gay, 2000; Ladson-Billings, 1995; Rosa & Orey, 2003). There has been consistent criticism against the maker movement, stemming from the fact that it does not include the existing making practices in the context of people of diverse cultural and ethnic groups, therefore, the doing of STEM and CT through the existing making practices in cultural and diverse contexts or supplementing them with the conventional making practices is not a focus (see Tan & Calabrese-Barton, 2018; Blikstein, 2020). For example, Dougherty is of the view that there

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may exist no making in such diverse cultural or ethnic backgrounds which may evidence, inform, supplement and centre stage the practices of conventional maker movement hence, there is the need to export what goes on in a makerspace into such locations (see Britton, 2015). Again, in a 2013 keynote address at Stanford's FabLearn Conference on digital fabrication in education, Leah Buechley (2013) described the MAKE organization as being focused on a narrow range of maker activities (primarily robotics, electronics, and vehicles) and even a narrower range of makers, with 85 percent of its magazine covers featuring white boys and men. Hereafter, it can be concluded that the activities of makerspaces in the United States and Europe have promoted STEM and CT as a neutral and culturally-free discipline removed from social values, diverse cultural and ethnic contexts (see D'Ambrosio, 1990). Of concern is how Western "exceptionalism" has a profound influence on non-Western education, in the sense that indigenous and non-conventional forms of STEM pedagogical approaches continue to be marginalized. These have resulted in school pupils, particularly in rural cultural communities, experiencing schooling as a one-way border crossing (Giroux, 1992), a situation that requires them to leave their home culture at the school gate and move into the alien culture of the school. However, as the maker movement is situated in the constructionist theory (Papert, 1993a), educators are helped to understand how different media can be used to express and transform multiple ideas in different contexts (Ackermann, 2001). Thus, the constructionists process could take many forms and shapes, in that, children might want to program a computer or build robots in ways that might violate the canonical rules of professional-coding and engineering-productively and creatively going against the grain of well-established practices in these technical fields, resulting in epistemological pluralism (Turkle & Papert, 1991). For example, how the maker of the Tlingit basket came up with the design that depicts a great understanding of Euclidean geometry is a puzzle (Mukhopadhyay, 2008). In Civil's (2016) analysis of a seamstress' practice, she noted that to make the pattern for a skirt, the seamstress made a quarter of a circle in such a way that it showed the circle as the locus of all points equidistant from a central point. Yet, these seamstress and Tlingit basket makers did not have a course in formal geometry, nor talk about Euclidean Geometry in their making. Similarly, In lieu of these STEM in such non-conventional makerspaces, I hypothesize the focus of making practices in diverse ethnic and cultural contexts (indigenous; cultural; craft; ethno making-see Blikstein, 2020; Bang & Barajas-López, 2018) as a form of making spaces (Tucker-Raymond & Gravel, 2019) by attempting a glocalised form of makerspaces that is situated in ethnomathematics (Ascher, 1991; Millroy, 1992; Gerdes, 1985). This serves as an avenue to increase and focalize research in the maker movement on the existing making in diverse ethnic and cultural context. In essence, this conceptual paper conceptualizes what doing STEM through the existing making practices in the context of people of diverse cultural and ethnic groups is and how that can also supplement, inform and centre stage the global practices of conventional maker movement.

Cultural making and ethnomathematics

D'Ambrosio (1990) defines *ethno* in the socio-cultural context as language, jargon, and codes of behavior, myths, and symbols as Blikstein (2020) defines making as a more general type of practice than only 3D printing, robotics, etc., enacted on basic or advanced materials. Combining Blikstein's (2020) and D'Ambrosio's (1990) definitions of "making" and "ethno", ethnomaking or cultural making may refer to a more general type of practice, enacted on basic or advanced materials, either with no or high technology within a specific cultural context which may evidence the doing of STEM. Ethnomaking comprises activities, materials, practices, and themes that are attuned to a more specific group, culture, or region (such as basket making, pottery, electronics upcycling, woodworking, or costume making) (Blikstein, 2020). An ethnomathematician will see ethnomaking as an avenue to discover the STEM concepts in the making of these activities, practices and materials. This process is to help reconstruct or 'unfreeze' STEM thoughts that are 'hidden' or 'frozen' in old techniques (see Gerdes, 1986). From an emic and etic perspective (Rosa & Orey, 2010), the artisan, who imitates a known production technique, is not doing STEM (emic). However, the artisan(s) who discovered the technique was/were thinking STEM (etic). An example is the geometric visualization of the weaver expressed through actions and materials (Ascher, 1994). As she puts it: ...the carpenter definitely is dealing with a mathematical idea; the mathematician who [arbitrarily decided to trisect an angle only with ruler and compass] was dealing with an idea. They are both important but they are different. And, they are linked (D'Ambrosio & Ascher, 1994, p. 38). It is as precise as an illustration in a schoolbook on geometry (Mukhopadhyay, 2008).

Glocalized making and ethnomathematics

For Branigan-Pipe (2016), the principles that shape the 21st Century Makerspace learning environments are those same principles that have guided the indigenous people for ages. For example, the first robot to walk the earth was a bronze giant called Talos, created by Hephaestus, the Greek god of invention. Inventing, making, tinkering and designing are indigenous practices (Gutiérrez, 2015). Glocalized making is the process of taking characteristic elements from the maker movement and infusing them into existing making practices in diverse culture and ethnic contexts. Such forms of making are supposed to be locally and globally relevant. Glocalized making supports historicized experiences as the making approach and practice by encouraging both indigenous and conventional makers to develop an understanding of the interconnecting relationship among ideology, power, and culture and rejects any claim to universal foundations for truth and culture, as well as any claim to objectivity (see Leistyina & Woodrum, 1996) in the maker movement. In glocalized making, the maker movement does not see the knowledge and practices of communities of diverse cultures and ethnic backgrounds as without maker culture and hence, awaiting the conventional maker movement deposits—what Freire (1970/2000) coined, "the 'banking' concept of education" (p. 72). Glocalization is a concept originally coined by business circles

and it means to create products for the global market, but customized to suit local cultures and tastes. The fundamental question of the glocalized making is about the compromise between what is already there in the culture, the practices, the materials, and the new elements from the maker movement that teachers or designers want to bring (see Blikstein, 2020). Glocalized making is to produce innovative ways of thinking and reasoning. Teachers can be engaged in the designing of 3-D and 2-D mathematical manipulatives and lessons, based on cultural making to anchor their pedagogical and conceptual knowledge. Also, teachers can be trained to introduce light up fashion and electronics into existing cultural making of indigenous textiles.

Conceptualizing cultural and glocalized making

A major problem with mathematics education in contemporary society is its overwhelming bias towards a Western orientation in its topics and research paradigm. A search for new approaches and methodologies is necessary to record historical forms of mathematical ideas that occur in different cultural contexts and to take advantage of the emerging globalization of business, science, religion, art, music, and other aspects of culture (Orey & Rosa, 2019). Numerous studies have demonstrated the sophisticated mathematical ideas and procedures that often include geometric principles in craftwork, architectural concepts, and practices in the activities and artifacts developed by many indigenous, local, and vernacular cultures (Eglash et al., 2006). Thus, ethnomodelling (Rosa & Orey, 2010) and ethnocomputing (Eglash et al., 2006). However, as noted by Rosa and Orey (2010), modelling is an essential tool for ethnomathematics. But when we create a model for a cultural artifact or practice, it is hard to know if we are capturing the right aspects; whether the model is accurately reflecting the mathematical ideas or practices of the artisan who made it, or imposing mathematical content external to the indigenous cognitive repertoire (Babbitt et al., 2012). Again, the mere pointing to a photograph of some intricate basket or monumental pyramid is not sufficient for engaging children or developing their mathematics skills. (Babbitt et al., 2012). Hence, the use of computational media to help address these challenges thus, ethnocomputing (Babbitt et al., 2012). However, ethnocomputing can be seen as an approach that might have subtracted the cultural aspect of cultural material through technology and computationalization. Again, as a criticism to ethnocomputing, what is known as a major challenge in the educational system in many communities of colour and low income is the inequality of educational resources which includes access to computers and other ICT materials. For example, in one experimental study of ethnocomputing (see Babbitt et al., 2015), it can be seen that the study computationalized the cultural making of Adinkra symbols from a rural Ghanaian community using computers and, implemented them in a Ghanaian city classroom. Could this be attributed to the fact that electricity and computers were not available in classrooms of such rural Adinkra making community? This is meant that students whose ideal cultural making was computationalized might have limited access to their transformed cultural making practice. As a note, “we have been programming for just a few decades, but people have been making for millennia” (Blikstein, 2020, p. 116). Hence,

why not focus on the cultural context and what goes on or glocalized such cultural making? Thus, focusing on the mathematics/STEM identifiable in the cultural making practices and/or supplementing it with conventional maker practices leads to a new approach and methodology which is necessary to record historical forms of mathematical/STEM ideas that occur in different cultural contexts, and to take advantage of the emerging globalization of business, science, religion, art, music and other aspects of culture thus, the need for cultural and glocalized making. Also, Mukhopadhyay (2008) stated, “given that throughout the known history of humankind people have always created music and dance, designed household objects, adorned their bodies with paints and designs, it is not unusual for anthropologists and others to examine where patterns come from” (p. 64). Franz Boas (1927/1955) wrote that: “No people [...] however hard their lives may be, spend all their time, all their energies in the acquisition of food and shelter [...] Even the poorest tribes have produced work that gives them aesthetic pleasure [...] [they] devote much of their energy to the creation of works of beauty” (p. 9). No matter how diverse the ideals may be, the general character of the enjoyment of beauty is of the same order everywhere. This realization points to the link between indigenous craftwork making and formal mathematics, computations, engineering, etc. namely an instinctive fascination with patterns. The knowledge of an indigenous “craft” – basket weaving, canoe making, for example – is complex and situated in cultural values and everyday living. For example, the construction of canoes for a non-Western group using indigenous material evolves over a substantial period of time incorporating cultural traditions of design, understanding of engineering, and adaptation to the environment. To an individual who does not belong to the community, the canoes, although functional and efficient, may look crude and primitive. If the individual happens to be trained in, and used to, only technologically-sophisticated building tools, the process of construction might seem to him/her as simplistic and rudimentary. As a consequence, both the process and the product of creating artefacts are not recognized as a cognitively complex process. Hence, an obvious reason why the maker movement does not contend such forms of making. In this regard, cultural and glocalized making draw on studies employing ethnomathematics, ethnomodelling and ethnocomputing as a framework to understand the computations and mathematics in the existing making practices in diverse cultural and ethnic contexts (Eglash et al., 2006; D’Ambrosio, 1990), and how those is supplemented to operate within the conventional maker movement. For example, through ethnocomputing, local designs have been analyzed as forms and the applications of symmetrical classifications from crystallography to indigenous textile patterns (Eglash at al., 2006) and these can be supplemented with electronics to produce e-textiles, thus glocalized making. On the other hand, ethnomathematics can use cultural and glocalized making as a tool to help reconstruct or ‘unfreeze’ the mathematical thinking that is ‘hidden’ or ‘frozen’ in old techniques, like, e.g., that of basket making. In ethnomodelling, Rosa and Orey (2006) modelled the mathematical knowledge that lace makers in the northeast of Brazil use to make patterns that have mathematical concepts not associated with traditional geometric principles. Here, cultural making seeks to rather observe and interpret the making processes from the lace

makers to identify the mathematical concepts. Again, glocalized making would empower the Brazilian lacemaker and students to introduce the concept of computer and electronic programming into such cultural making (see Jayathritha & Kafai, 2019). Again, mediated activity through the lace making can be derived for teachers to be engaged in the designing of 3-D and 2-D mathematical manipulatives to anchor their pedagogical and conceptual knowledge through a reflection of such cultural making in the conventional maker world, hence glocalized making. I define these connections as cultural and glocalized making, which is the act of identifying the making practices in diverse cultural and ethnic contexts to identify STEM, and also supplementing, informing and centrestaging it with practices of conventional maker movement. In this context, Figure 1 shows a conceptualisation of cultural and glocalized making, as the intersection of three fields of knowledge: cultural anthropology, ethnomathematics, and the maker movement.

Figure 1: Cultural and glocalized making as the intersecting region of three knowledge fields

From Figure 1, the intersection between the maker movement and ethnomathematics relates to the global representation of diverse ethnic and cultural groups in the maker movement and hence, respect and the valorization of the tacit knowledge (Rosa & Orey, 2007). Also, traditions found in diverse contexts, and often the students therein, will be enabled to uncover the mathematical/STEM concepts hidden in the making of cultural artifacts and supplement these with practices of conventional maker movement. Therefore, it becomes necessary to begin by using sociocultural contexts, realities, and interests or unique needs of students and not mere enforcement of a rigid set of external curricular rules and values with often decontextualized activities (Rosa & Orey, 2007). This approach brings about the supplement, and centre stage between the maker movement and cultural anthropology in order to reach critical transitivity (Freire, 1998). According to Rosa and Orey (2007), diverse forms of local knowledge develop the context, source, and form for what is found in the intersection between mathematics and cultural anthropology and occurs when members of distinct cultural groups use it to solve problems faced in their own contexts. It also becomes a profound body of knowledge often built up by these members over time and across generations of living in close contact with their own historical, social, cultural, and

natural environment (D'Ambrosio, 1990). This context uses a definition of cultural making as the uncovering, unfreezing, and supplementing mathematical ideas, notions, procedures, and practices in which the prefix ethno relates to the specific mathematical knowledge possessed by the members of distinct cultural groups, where ethnomathematics adds cultural perspectives to the mathematics discovered through making. Hence, it results in addition of cultural perspectives also to the maker movement. In the glocalized making process, global mathematical knowledge through maker movement must supplement and be adapted to local mathematics in the making practices in diverse cultural and ethnic contexts.

Methodology for recognizing or identifying STEM through cultural making

In this section, I propose a demonstration of making in the cultural and glocalized form as a pedagogical approach that challenges the conventional way of thinking or doing mathematics/STEM in the maker movement. This approach is also a form of an ethnographic and design-based inquiry where researchers participate in cultural making activities.

The Gerdes (1985) approach

Gerdes (1985) looked to the geometrical forms and patterns of traditional objects like baskets, mats, pots, houses, fish traps, etc. and posed the question: why do these material products possess the form they have? In order to answer this question, he learned the usual production techniques and tried to vary the forms. By this process of rediscovering the mathematical thinking hidden in these baskets and fish traps – and in other traditional production techniques – the future teachers personally feel stimulated to reconsider the value of their cultural heritage: in fact, geometrical thinking was seen as not alien to their culture. This “unfreezing of culturally frozen mathematics” can serve, in many ways, as a starting point and source of inspiration for doing and elaborating other interesting mathematics. Another method for identifying the STEM in cultural making is by using Bishop’s (1988) mathematical activities model. This model consists of identifying how counting, locating, measuring, designing, playing, and explaining is done in the cultural making process.

The glocalized method

“Unfreezing frozen mathematics” through cultural making forces mathematicians and philosophers to reflect on the relationship between geometrical thinking and material production, between doing mathematics and technology (see Gerdes, 1985b). The latter enforcement, thus the relationship between doing mathematics and technology focalizes cultural making in the lens of conventional making to eradicate how technology and computations have subtracted the cultural aspect of maker movement. Hence, through the ethnographic studies by using the Gerdes (1985), there lies the opportunity for design research through socio-cultural theory grounded in mediated activity derived from Vygotsky (1978) for teachers to be engaged in the designing of 3-D and 2-D mathematical manipulatives, robotics and electronic programming to anchor their pedagogical and conceptual knowledge through a reflection of such cultural making in the conventional

maker world. This creates an opportunity to use such cultural making practices in a globalized context, which is glocalization.

Conclusion and final considerations

It is apparent, to this end, to assert that maker movement has sidelined existing making practices in the context of people of diverse cultural and ethnic groups whereas mathematics education considers these aspects. In order for this situation to be reconciled, the teaching and learning of mathematics need to be reconsidered. In essence, there must be a link between culture and making as a pedagogical approach that is informed by ethnomathematics. For example, teachers can be engaged in the designing of 3-D and 2-D mathematical manipulatives, robots, electronics programming and lessons that are based on cultural making to accentuate students' pedagogical and conceptual knowledge. This situation provides the basis or the starting point, as well as a source of inspiration, for doing and elaborating mathematics and not merely learning about it. The proposed cultural and glocalized pedagogical approach for teaching and learning mathematics in this paper serves as a basis to reconsider the conventional way of thinking or learning mathematics in the maker movement. It is evident that the approach is particularly helpful in the sense that students are able to formulate their own concepts by situating them within their cultural contexts and also linked to conventional and other global practices. Through the combined use of methods from Gerdes (1985), Bishop (1988) and Vygotsky (1978), in the sphere of ethnographic studies and design-based research, studies in this area of research will reveal how the cultural and glocalized approach can supplement, inform, and centre stage the global practices of conventional making to the maker movement when situated in ethnomathematics.

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